

Cyber Victimization: School Experience of Malaysian Cyberbullied Teenagers

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Abstract—Cyberbullying among schoolchildren and teenagers became a hot issue discussed by Malaysian society. Cyberbullying is a new age of bullying because it uses the modern digital technology intentionally to hurt and degrade someone in the cyber world. Cyberbullying is a problem affecting many teenagers as they embrace online communication and interaction whereby virtual world with no borders. By adopting a qualitative approach, this study has captured 8 cyberbullied victims' school experience. Even years after leaving school, these 8 cyberbullied victims remember how it feels to be bullied in the cyber world. The principal investigator also tries to identify the possibility factors that contribute to cyberbullying among these 8 victims. The result shows that these victims were bullied differently in cyber world. This study not just primarily focuses on cyberbullying issues among schoolchildren and teenagers; it also addresses the motives and causes of cyberbullying. Lastly, this article will be served as guidance for school teachers, parents and teenagers to prepare to tackle cyberbullying together. Cyberbullying is no laughing matter in our community, and it is time to spread the seeds of peace inspires others to do the same.

Keywords—Cyberbullying, cyber victimization, internet, school experience, teenagers.

I. INTRODUCTION

CYBERBULLYING among Malaysian schoolchildren/teenagers is increasing and more and more talked in Malaysian newspapers. It became a hot issue discussed by Malaysian society. This shows just how urgent actions by the relevant authorities need to ensure that this issue does not continue to grow. In Malaysia, cyberbullying is referred by using the internet or any other electronic technology devices such as cellphones, computers or tablets to send mean, harmful and aggressive messages through e-mails, websites, text messages via social media, leaving the victim feeling harmful and powerless [1]. People should distinguish between cyberbullying which is usually happening between children and youth and cyber harassment and stalking which is usually done among adolescents. Empirical research shows teenagers who experience cyberbullying either the victims/bullies, report low self-esteem [2] deep depression and suicidal intention [3], [4] and increasing in school discipline or social problems and participation in some other problematic offline manners [2], [5]. The danger of cyber world could be seen through these eight cyberbullied victims' stories and let it be an eye-opener to all. Cyberbullying can impact negatively on emotional well-being and academic progress of schoolchildren/teenagers

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who are bullied. This study also discusses the problems, possibilities causes and effects of cyberbullying among secondary school students which occurs inside and outside of school compound. There are many causes that contribute to cyberbullying such as environmental influences and friends. Appropriate preventive measures need to be highlighted by the education policy makers, school, parents and the community in preventing cyberbullying. Comfortable, fear-free and safe school environment is needed to generate healthy process of teaching and learning. Cyberbullying is no laughing matter and can cause inconvenience to others such mental health issue. Lastly, this study is expected to enable schoolchildren/teenagers to understand, identify types of bullying and to create awareness among the schoolchildren/teenagers of cyberbullying; implications for schools and families are discussed with the goal of mitigating cyberbullying and its negative outcomes among adolescent populations.

II. PURPOSE OF STUDY

Briefly, the purpose and objectives of this research and specific aims are as follows:

- To see the difference in cyberbullying and traditional bullying.
- To identify the possibility motives and causes of cyberbullying among teenagers.
- To see how the disadvantaged teenagers (e.g. disabilities, facial appearance, skin-color, language) cope with cyberbullying.
- To see the effect of psychological, physical and emotional cyberbullying and towards its victims.
- To see how cyberbullying affects their adjustment in social school settings environment and how effectively parental and teachers involvement to combat cyberbullying.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature used in this study contains information global and local context. The purpose is analysing studies and research from a global context to point out cyberbullying can affect a child/teenager welfare, wellbeing, and social development. When searching for literature and relevant sources, these became an apparent struggle to find specific information with regards to the effect of cyberbullying among teenagers and more specifically affect their behavior. By understanding cyberbullying among teenagers is necessary to enable us to find appropriate methods or approaches to address and overcome this issue. The problem of cyberbullying should be solved immediately so that it would not affect the academic

progress, social development and the personality of the students.

A. Definition of Cyberbullying

According to [6], cyberbullying occurs when someone using electronic devices such as cell phone or social media by posting mean, intimidating or threatening messages about a person online to upset someone. Cyberbullying is defined as an intentional, willful and repeated harm committed through the use of cell phones, computer, electronic or social media devices [7] to hurt and embarrass someone inappropriately on the Internet [8]. According to [9], cyberbullying is an aggressive intentional act carried out via Internet to bring discomfort to someone.

B. Difference and Similarity between Traditional Bullying and Cyberbullying

According to [10], traditional bullying behaviour is an aggressive behaviour that is carried out repeatedly to people individually and collectively. It is also a form of social interaction in which dominant individual (bully) will show aggressive behavior that is likely causing discomfort and pain to individuals who are less dominant, timid or weak. Researchers have identified 3 types of traditional bullying as physical, verbal and relational [11]-[13]. Antisocial behavior refers as indirect bullying.

According to [11], boys are generally more violent in bullying compared to girls. Girls have seen more in verbal bullying such as, ridicule, humiliation, name calling, taunting, intimidating, boycott, racial labelling, slander, gossiping and manipulating in social relationships.

Cyberbullying is harder to control than traditional bullying, the harm and emotional discomfort is less observable and difficult to measure or identify in online environment [5]. Online content can go viral easily than offline content. A single post can be viewed and shareable by others. It is the ongoing nature of cyberbullying when the victim constantly worries about what the perpetrator will do next [14]. The good thing is the target can change his or her daily patterns to avoid personal contact with the bully online.

According to [15], the victims exhibit more aggressive behavior in cyberspace than in real life. Gender studies show that female victims may lose focus easily compared to male victims [16]. In cyberbullying, the bully is faceless, with strong supporters, viewers or audience. There are possibilities that the victims are affected permanently.

The similarity between cyberbullying and traditional bullying is distinguished by cruel intention, repetition, harm; mischief and power of imbalance [5], [17]. In order to distinguish between traditional bullying and cyberbullying, cyberbullying has no physical borders. Cyberbullying happens in cyberspace easily and fast without knowing whom to be blamed and responsible. In most cases, the perpetrators are remained anonymous in cyberspace by sending hurtful messages to attack and upset the victims. The perpetrators are free to express their mind and thought in cyber world without any physical interaction with their victims unlike traditional

bullying. However, traditional bullying and cyberbullying have the similar impact; it leaves a deep mark in the heart of the victims [18].

C. The Possibility of Cause and Effect of Cyberbullying

According to [19], the children are exposing themselves to cybercrime at a tender age. The changes of modern technology have encouraged negative behavior among young children for example cyberbullying.

According to a survey "Online Bullying among Youth 8-17 Years Old in Malaysia" by Microsoft Corporation in 2012, Malaysia is ranked 17th the highest in online bullying among 25 countries surveyed. The awareness and knowledge of online bullying is substantially lower than average. 77% of survey respondents agreed that cyberbullying is one of the latest techniques online predators target their victims. Online bullying of others is below average. Malaysian parents take very little precaution to protect their children from online bullying. Only 38% of respondents are concerned with the issue and 27% of parents talk to their children about the risks of online communication. In addition, only 13% of parents ask their children if they have been bullied online (compared to the global average of 30%). So far, in Malaysia there is no proper or formal school policies implemented to raise awareness of cyberbullying [20].

The statistical report by the Cyber Security Malaysia in 2007 showed a total of 60 cases have been reported and treated as cyberbullying. Although the report described and treated as isolated case, it did not stop cyberbullying. Cyberbullying is happening around the globe like an epidemic including Malaysia. However, cyberbullying is taken seriously in USA. Almost 40% of the students in USA had been a victim of cyberbullying. They students have a very high suicidal thought because they could not bear the insult and humiliation by their schoolmates via social media [21].

Research has found that cyberbullying is related to negative emotions such as suicidal thought, social isolation, anxiety, anger, fear, low self-esteem, depression, self-hate and humiliation [22], [23] and these emotions have been associated with adolescents' delinquency or interpersonal violence [24], [25].

D. School and Parental Involvement to Combat Cyberbullying

School counsellor can provide professional training for parents, guardians' and school staff to reduce the risk of cyberbullying among schoolchildren/teenagers [26], [27]. Teachers and parents ought to know and understand the usage of modern technology by showing concern how schoolchildren/teenagers communicate online and how exactly cyberbullying occurs.

Student training or classroom guidance to confront cyberbullying by including students' capabilities which help teenagers to understand consequences of cyberbullying improve social problem-solving and build up the ability to care of the cyberbullying victims [28], [29]. Students who witness when cyberbullying is happening online (offline)

should stand up and support one another [30].

IV. RESEARCH DESIGN

This study is expected to enable the schoolchildren/teenagers to understand, identify types of bullying and to create awareness among them about cyberbullying.

Reference [31] suggests that when interviewing the respondents the principal investigator(s) ought to consider the participant respondents, always safeguard human rights, interest and sensitivity, communicate research objectives and lastly protect the privacy of the participants. Extra care must be taken by the researcher to avoid judgements and personal bias among people that are dominated, oppressed or have less power and authority than the researcher.

The data were collected via a semi-structured questions technique amongst 8 cyberbullied victims. They were mutual friends, acquaintances and neighbors of the writer. They were asked to recall their past school experience in a 3 weeks in-depth interview and analysis. After the interviews were transliterated they were carefully read so that the specific data and issues can be detected in order to analyze, compare and discuss. All participants were asked the similar questions for easy compare and analysis process.

The selection of participants is the primary step in the data gathering process and it is based on two main criteria. Firstly, they are volunteered to participate in the research interview. Secondly, they have experienced cyberbullying during their schooling days. Participants are recruited based on voluntary participation. The writer faced difficulties of recruiting participants through random sampling because the nature of the study requires a considerable amount of time and effort from the participants to be interviewed. The writer decided to turn to her mutual friends, acquaintances and neighbors who volunteered to participate in this study. They expressed their interest and would like to share their cyberbullying experience with the others.

Before the official interview process begun, the writer had a preliminary meeting with the participant in order to establish trust, review critical considerations and complete consent form as a protection to the respondents. It is easier when the intended use of data is clear, specific and distinctive [32].

Honesty is the main focus when working with mutual friends, acquaintances and neighbors. It is essential to keep a high level of confidentiality, flexibility and ingenuity throughout the interview process. Since the participants came from different background they would tell stories from different aspects as a victim. Additional research from a variety of age groups, gender and cross-culturally would add another layer of understanding about cyberbullying among secondary school students/teenagers in Malaysia.

Interview Outline:

1. How was your school life or schooling experience back then? Be as specific and detailed as possible.
2. How were your teachers or schoolmates? Were they kind?
3. Did they ever embarrass you intentionally in public?
4. Did you get enough attention from your teachers, parents or friends?

5. When did you first become a victim of cyberbullying?
6. What forms did the cyberbullying take?
7. Why did people target you? Be as specific and detailed as possible.
8. Did you get cyberbullied in school online and offline including (verbal/ physical/ emotional/sexual bias)?
9. How did the cyberbullying affect you?
10. How did you cope and overcome cyberbullying?
11. How has the cyberbullying affected who you are today?
12. Did your past bad schooling experience haunt you daily?
13. What are your suggestions to combat cyberbullying?

V. RESEARCH FINDING AND DISCUSSION

In today's new world of advanced modern technology, cyberbullying is far from uncommon. In modern days, bullies are no longer pushing you into lockers, ground, they do not tell their victims to meet them behind schoolyard after school. They disguise behind fake user names and profiles from miles away constantly criticizing, mocking and abusing the innocent good people because they know the good ones rarely fight back because they know the good ones rarely fight back because they are frightened and might encounter more retaliation. Pseudonyms are used to protect the participants in this study.

Even many years have passed; Ivan expressed how upset he was with his physical appearance and cyberbullying experience he had in secondary school. Cyberbullying can affect a person for many years, just like any other traumatic experience. According to [33], schoolchildren need to feel safe and be protected from strongly negative emotional experience especially in school.

"My teenage life was completely a nightmare on my birthday. I was involved in motorcycle accident with a friend. He had a head concussion and I almost lost one foot. Everyone in school accused me for the accident. After the accident, I started to receive hundreds of hateful messages online such as Twitter, Facebook and for my wrong do and some even accused me as the main culprit of the accident. I constantly absent from school for treatment, sometimes I skipped school because I did not felt like going. Some schoolmates were quite nasty because they had to accommodate me especially on laboratory science experiments. Some started to post my pictures online and wished I was vanished or dead. I was a burden. The girls hissed at me whenever they seen me. The boys would scorn and cursed me verbally. The worst, I was called "crippled". I did not tell anymore or want my parents to worry. A lot of my schoolmates choose to ignore me. I did the same. My hair began to fall out through the stress, although I attended counselling session but helpless."

The writer begins to consider whether these shared cyberbullied experience contributed to mental health issue and social problems. Schoolchildren/teenagers that have been "labeled" negatively by their peers tended to remain constant throughout their life and resulted in negative social relationship with others because young brains prone to

remember strong negative experiences based on their guilt.

Jane recalled how her parents went to see her schoolteachers to express their concern about cyberbullying. Jane elaborated by saying:

“I came from a mixed-parentage background. Since childhood, I did not have many friends because of my cultural background. The girls would not play with me. The boys would make fun of my name. I cried alone because I did not fit in. I was never welcomed. I told my parents but they did not understand. I thought things would change as these bullies grew older but I was wrong. As I entered to secondary school, I encountered something even bigger- cyberbully. My parents would come to my school on Open Day. I looked completely different from them. Schoolmates started to post online I was liar, telling fib about my mixed parentage, making remarks about my appearance such as fat and ugly and etc. It went viral online. The girls put vicious messages on e-mails, Twitter, Facebook page and whole cyberbullying campaign against me. Hurtful words mocked me from the computer screen whenever I went online even from the privacy of my home. I felt suffocating. My parents brought and printed the e-mails and comments about me online to the attention of the principal. No action was taken but at least we managed to bring the issue up. I changed school. I never heard from those nasty people again. As we moved into a new neighbourhood, schoolmates quickly accepted my warmth and friendliness because they celebrated cultural diversity.”

The writer reckons that it is odd to believe bullying/cyberbullying can begin at any age unknowingly by the parents. Being bullied during childhood can lead to low self-esteem and emotional depression and suicidal thought as adult [10], [34]. Every child deserves the right to be safe regardless their ethnicity, race or religion. It is our role as parents, community members, neighbors, technology providers, school administrators to be alert and notify the relevant authorities when a child is facing cyberbullying either online/offline. To protect children from cyberbullying must be identified quickly so they could receive support service and culprit must be immediately caught. Kate shared that:

“I am a swim coach. I was once a cyberbullied victim.

It allowed me to stop running from my past. Instead of letting others to tear me apart, I am capable to live my life to the fullest and inspiring others to stand up to cyberbullies. When I was 16, I transferred to a new school because of my father’s job. I joined the school swimming team because I used to represent my former school in swimming competition. I won many medals. Perhaps, I rubbed the wrong shoulder. My triumph turned to jealousy. My new schoolmates were targeting me online by spreading malicious rumour. I could not handle harsh remarks. I was humiliated. Girls in the swimming club started to dislike me and some ignoring me. I was heartbroken and sad. It lasted for nearly a year. I lost concentration and interest in swimming, my grades and

swimming skill declining greatly. I became anti-social and disliked school. My parents reported what was happening to my teachers. For those nasty girls who spreading online malicious rumours received warning letters from school and attended counselling session. As a sport person, throughout the miserable months of “cyberbullying”, I learned an important self-taught lesson, such as how never to read a hateful text or messages. Whenever I see nasty messages about me, I would delete it before reading it.”

Traits such as popularity, physical strength/appearance, self-confidence, race and ethnicity can give an online perpetrators prey on the targets easily, for example Jane and Kate [10], [35].

The writer reckons some children and teenagers sometimes become angry and resentful on what others have. This could be anything, good academic or sports achievements, popularity, or even a particular girlfriend or boyfriend. Jealousy can lead to anger and resentment. It depends on how a person manages these emotions. There are many healthy ways to release anger and frustration but not all teenagers are aware of it.

Lisa recalled her suicidal intention that left a deep mark in her heart. Cyberbullying can lead to low self-esteem and suicidal intention [36], [37]. The writer thinks, based on traditional bullying/cyberbullying facts and worldwide statistics, the fact is horrendous. If this many children are being bullied daily in school or cyber world over the years facing physical and emotional tortured, imagine how many will become dangerously suicidal? How many will have thoughts of revenge and turn to homicidal fantasies into reality? Such negative act does not have to happen. Lisa elaborated by saying:

“I love singing since childhood. Singing reminds me of my late mother. She died of cancer when I was 17. We used to sing together. I always posted our singing videos online. A lot of messages littered with insults and personal attacks saying I was a lousy singer. I knew who did it, my schoolmates. I reported to my teacher. It turned the matter worst. I was “trapped” in the cyber world. I was devastated and frightened. My mother, she was the strength for me to go on. We sang together until her last dying breath. Even after her death, the girls left vicious messages on my Facebook and Twitter page created in memory of her. I received hundreds abusive and hurtful messages online mocking my loss and blamed my voice that killed my mother. Some even sending death notes to me. After enduring this sort of abuse for a long time; I decided to end my life by committing suicide but each time I was saved by father. My father was devastated and disappointed. He printed all the abusive messages from my Facebook and Twitter pages sent it to the police because he knew the school would not care.”

Victim of violent crime [38] negligence and abuse [39] suffer from significant feelings of embarrassment and guilt closely related to psychology problem and personal social development failures. Insecurity, self-conscious and traumatized emotion is common especially on victims that

falsely accused of stealing like Mike. Mike mentioned that,

“I came from a poor single parent family with many siblings. Owning a cell phone or computer was impossible for us. We knew the importance of modern technology. The only time we got contact with computer was during ICT lesson. One day, I was invited to a birthday party. I was accused and caught “red-handed” for stealing a cell phone by one of the parents. Someone put the cell phone into my bag. I tried to explain the situation but no one believed me. I never thought they would put my photos online. My schoolmates started upload their comments calling me “thief”. There were various comments about my poor family background and stealing reasons. Ever since that incident, I lost all my friends, they either joined in the nasty online conversation or were too afraid to say anything. I was left alone. Some boys boycotted me. Some even checked their wallets or pockets before and after speaking to me. The ugly rumours went on for months until it caught the attention of my discipline teacher. I told him what exactly happened. He did voice up on my behalf to prove my innocence but the negative perceptions about me never stopped. Whenever, someone lost their things in school, I was always being blamed until I was proven innocent. It went on for years until I left secondary school. I never spoke to my mother about it because I was ashamed and wanted to move on.”

The writer thinks that schoolchildren/teenagers should be careful and cautious about sharing picture of them as they would not know who is misusing them. We want schoolchildren/teenagers to take precautions when posting their photos online. Once the “embarrassing” pictures or videos are uploaded, they are remaining online forever and it will continue to haunt the victim. Nina expressed her experience by:

“I was ridiculed and humiliated by my peers and seniors at secondary school in person and online. The memory is still fresh even many years have passed by. The only crime that I did was forwarding a photo of me to a popular boy in school that I fancy when I was 15. One girl from my school borrowed the boy’s phone found the images and forwarded it to other students. The image found its way to more students in my school and some in other school. Since, my school was located in a school district. I turned into a laughing stock. The boy that I fancy put on his media page and called me “complete loser”. I had been subjected to cruel taunts and insult from peers and seniors in school. I was verbally abused and teased in school. More and more bullying messages on my Facebook page, some created online groups dedicated to calling me foul names. Many people secretly hate me. My parents contacted the school but the school administrators not prepared or even ready to help. The school did not have specific plan or mechanism against cyberbullying. The just offered their sympathy. I deleted my Facebook and Twitter pages. That was the only way I could stop it by controlling people access to me. That

was hard but not responding became easier than trying to argue with those cyberbullies who never stopping harassing.”

The greatest childhood school fear is being criticised for poor academic or sports performance of any kind in front of schoolmates and becoming a laughing stock that literally leads to bullying. According to [40], embarrassing situations do reduce a child’s learning potential because their brains learn to avoid participation to reduce the risk of becoming laughing stock. Their self-control emotion is under stress. With such negative childhood experience and thought, it would not be surprised if the bullied victim enters a new classroom or school, they communicate their insecurity, anxiety and worry to their schoolmates, setting themselves up for more victimization [41]. Owen elaborated by saying,

“I was given to foster parents when I was 10. Both of my parents were killed in a car accident. I had hard times adjusting my new life and was not comfortable to share my problems and dilemma with anyone. Through my primary school days, I was often being bullied into everything due to my weight, poor academic and quiet nature. I had no one to share my problems with and felt very depressed. I did not want my foster parents to worry because I was living under their roof. Upon moving to secondary school, bullying did not stop but got more complicated. I became victim of cyberbullying. Those boys who used to bully me in primary school enrolled to the same secondary school as me. They started to influence some other new boys to hate me. People started to believe what the rumours said. Car crash photo were posted on line with nasty comment that I killed my parents. Up to certain extend, I started to think what they were saying was true. I had no friends. Almost every day of my school life, I would have recess alone. There were times school prefects would join me but seldom. One day, during recess few boys came to mock and beat me. I did not even disturb them. It happened too quickly. I stood up for the first time and I gave them nicely. We were sent to the principal. We all got expelled over the fight. I felt regretted about it. I realized what I did was wrong I tried to fight back but actually I was fighting with myself. My foster parents enrolled me to a private school. I was sent to counselling and therapy session but it did help me coping with anxiety and emotional depression. The wound in my heart remains forever.”

Phil recalled how the “taboo” nature of gay links with femininity. Gay term was used as an option for insulting any boy because they provided the ultimate and extreme insult. Gay terms were also used for generalized abuse against on boys who were suspicious for being insufficiently masculine [42], [43]. Phil also discussed how his attitude and behavior was typically associated with femininity which assumed weakness and inferiority [44]. As a result, it is no surprise that such boys who represented femininity were labelled as gay and constantly bullied. Indicators of effeminacy included “girlish” speech and mannerism, playing “girls” games, the displaying of “girlish” taste in music, arts, fashion or even the

avoidance of attending PE lesson [45].

“My father owns few clothing factories. I become “addicted” to fashion even I was born as a boy. Since childhood, instead seeing myself playing with the boys, I would spend my time in the factory designing clothes for men. As I enrolled to all boys’ school, my passion became my greatest fear. Most boys outcast me due to my neat appearance, I was not sporty enough. Some even called me “gay”. Some boys started to post online, spreading rumours about me wearing women’s clothes and some hoped I would die of AIDS. I could not handle what others said which only added my sense of otherness and loneliness. My privacy was invaded whenever I tried to speak to other boys in school compound. Some boys would spy on me then they started to spread more gossips on me online. It made me paranoid. I started to think what they were saying was real. I had no friends. I did not even dare to go to washroom during recess. I waited until lesson time. Some nasty boys would splash water at me if I were seen in washroom with them. During PE lesson, the boys would make jokes insulting me as “gay” in changing room. I always asked for dismissed during PE lesson. My PE teacher aware of it but my voice never heard. I became bitter about life. My Facebook, Internet blog was covered with swear and abusive words. I deleted it even I spent quite amount of time to build it. My fashion creation and ideas were in it. I had the right to be online as much as anyone else. I suffered in silence until I graduated even I knew those boys behind it but I could not help myself. I knew bullies would always learn to use new technology to go against others. People can be cruel online and hiding in disguise.”

The writer reckons that hateful or resentful anti-LGBT (lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender) rhetoric is nearly pervasive in Malaysian schools, putting students especially teenagers into silence; self-loathing, and self-harm. A man in love with fashion does not mean he is gay; it just happens he is into fashion. Being a fashion lover has nothing to do with “gay” or homosexual. It is based on one’s preferences. The most important thing to combat slur word such as “homo” is to alert the teachers or education policy makers with appropriate information to have LGBT topics included in the curriculum. Cyberbullying is widespread and sometimes is quite brutal in Malaysian secondary schools. The government ought to come up with valuable policies aimed at fixing the problem.

The 8 interviewed participants have been through a great ordeal of their life, their unfavorable school experience certainly have had left a deep mark in their social development during their teenage life especially Phil, Owen, Ivan and Mike because they did not pursue the online attackers due to embarrassment, fear, and simply not knowing what to do. Unlike Jane, Nina, Kate and Lisa, they enlightened their parents, school personnel and authorities. Their parents did not wish to see them suffer in silence by letting the perpetrators to walk free. Studies show, female victims tend to ask for help more than males victims [41]. They enlightened the school and authority before matters turned awry. Based on their

experience, there was no difference between their online and offline lives. Bullying was still bullying wherever it happened. Cyberbullying is like an extension of “offline” relationship. Social media has transformed into an epidemic that follows you everywhere because cyberbullies would always learn to use new technology to prey on their victims. For every one case which is reported thousands of other cyberbullying cases go unreported around worldwide. Talk is cheap, the vital matters are maximized only when the public take immediate action to combat cyberbullying. Let us turn from a worrying challenge to a motivation by protecting our children online.

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the experiences of these 8 cyberbullied victims, the paper reveals that cyberbullying among teenagers emerges most commonly from relationship problems such as jealousy, ganging up, physical appearances, family issue, and tolerance. The victims experience has left powerful negative effects on them especially on their emotion and social well-being. The reactive behavior from behavior form school/administrators, students are generally uncooperative, passive, inappropriate and ineffective.

Technology advancement has created new challenges and obstacles for schools in keeping students from harm. The goal of this research is to give school administrators/leaders, parents and students a greater understanding of cyberbullying phenomenon and suggest steps to deal or reduce the chance of cyberbullying. Meanwhile, the paper also serves as an implication for educational policy and practice to make the school as healthy ground to learn and study.

What happens on the World Wide Web is a reflection of society at large. Protection of minor is not the purview of a few but the responsibility of all. Implementation and management of monitoring and surveillance mechanism ought to be taken in school to ensure schoolchildren are protected from harm in the cyber world.

Cyberbullying is like faceless people who put the innocent, fragile being into a burning building that he/she feels no way out. When you turn on your computer, tablet, cell phone, the cyberbullies are there.

Cyberbullies are total cowards; they hide behind the Internet and their advanced technology gadgets to insult others. As a good citizen, we should work hand in hand to combat cyberbullying and that people should make the most things like privacy settings to help each other and avoiding becoming cyberbullying victims. It makes the writer thinks; everyone can be cruel in cyber world.

Parents ought to educate themselves about the cyberbullying. Prevention through home education can stop cyberbullying. Many parents are overly isolated. They have no idea the harm of cyber world. Parents need to explain what is right and wrong to their children when connect to the virtual world. Schools should implement prevention of cyberbullying starting from preschool curriculum. Cyberbullying is like an epidemic, we should not think it is a part of growing up.

It would be more successful if the Ministry of Education could train more teachers who can counsel problem students

as well as enhance effective communication skill among teachers and parents. We need more teachers who can help students cope with emotional problems and matters related to mental health or combat cyberbullying and bullying issues. Schools should tighten procedures and circulars related to school discipline for instance students with disciplinary issues ought to undergo counselling session. Counselling workshop emphasizing on psychology and sociological aspects ought to be attend by all teachers enable them to help cyberbullying children/teenagers. Each school should work with professional counseling from welfare offices for many teachers. Careful professional steps need to be taken since Malaysia is multi-cultured society.

We suggest that the headmaster/principals and teachers need to equip with effective communication skill when talking to the parents about cyberbullying (bullying) issue. Firstly, the teachers of today are not authorized to react in a suitable manner due to their every powers have been curbed. Secondly, the parents and pupils/ students' of today are a whole lot different from parents/ students of yesteryears. Majority of the pupils/students are undisciplined nowadays, do not respect elders as well as teachers and are made to believe the schools owes them everything. One of the reasons for this pathetic state is because the new phenomenon of cyberbullying has crept into most schools. Proper mechanism should include the establishment of registry of cyber law to ensure minors are protected in schools, homes and communities.

Parents must be responsible for their children and must be made responsible, undisciplined students must be transferred to schools in other states, perhaps after two warning letters from the school administrators, if they do this the parents will wake up and do the necessary while the teachers can concentrate on teaching.

The trouble is many cyberbullied (bullied) schoolchildren/teenagers; they do not know how to seek for help especially the victims because they feel alone and insecure. They feel threaten and might receive further abuse. Meanwhile, a lot of parents do not realize why their children (cyberbullying victims and bullies) feeling extremely anxious and depressed. By getting proper help such as professional counselling session treatment can significantly help schoolchildren/teenagers to combat cyberbullying. The worst thing you can do is suffer in silence.

We are standing firm to spread our concern and care that cyberbullying is not acceptable around the globe. The horrific crimes hidden by the danger and dark website will be revealed, more culprits will be caught and more schoolchildren/teenagers will be saved from further harm. We must work together with law enforcement and other regulatory agencies to combat cyberbullying. Lastly, the writer would like to urge the society- a line has been crossed and any further escalation in irresponsible tactics use against the cyberbullying victims would represent a very real security risk. We need to work together collectively to prevent cyberbullying and provide a healthy learning environment to all.

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